

Waste management through a waste bank based on entrepreneurial readiness in Ngalang Village

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ABSTRACT

This research describes entrepreneurial readiness in the waste bank community at Ngalang Village, Gunungkidul Regency. This study is qualitative phenomenological research. This study's respondents were six administrators and members of the waste bank community in Ngalang Village, Gedangsari, Gunungkidul. Respondents were selected using a purposive sampling technique with the characteristics of the respondents: administrators and members of the Ngalang Village waste bank, do not have a permanent job, have an active status, and have been involved for at least one year. The data analysis employed in this research is content analysis. The results of the study show that the entrepreneurial readiness of the waste bank community in Ngalang Village has the skills needed in business, is courageous in dealing with and anticipating business failures, has a social network community that supports business activities, can see business opportunities, and prepare business development plans. In addition, in the waste bank community, they can prepare physically, mentally, and spiritually, have strong personalities, are willing to develop their skills, prepare for business activity, and prepare themselves for marketing the products. This entrepreneurial readiness will eventually become the principal capital in starting a business in the waste bank community.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Domestic waste causes flooding, environmental pollution, and bad effects on public health. They also take up land resources, pollute the environment, and breed pests and bacteria [1]. It has been noted that improper solid waste disposal and management can lead to air, soil, and water pollution because it clogs drains, creating stagnant water for insect breeding and transmission of diseases such as cholera [2]. Without adequate handling, waste will become an environmental disaster for society. We can manage integrated waste management by applying the 3R concept: reducing, reusing, and recycling. 3R waste management is an ideal solution to overcome the environmental, health, and economic problems caused by increasing waste and pollution [3]. This waste management requires an active role from the community, starting by separating the types of waste to be disposed of. People's awareness and participation significantly contribute to controlling the existing waste problems [4]. Education to the public regarding complex environmental issues is needed to

form a social awareness movement. Waste bank community s' participation could be enhanced by hosting various social activities at the grassroots level [5].

The community can make efforts to preserve the environment from waste through waste bank activities. Samadikun *et al.* [6] state that waste management can be integrated using a community-based waste bank activity. The community realizes that the existence of a waste bank provides excellent benefits for everyday life, including reducing waste generation (73.9%), the community is motivated to manage waste in everyday life (60.9%), as well as being profitable for the community's economy (43.5%) [6]. The study found a significant relationship between knowledge, attitudes, and actions and involvement in garbage banks. Furthermore, the results showed that trash bank customers exhibited better knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours than non-waste bank customers [7]. Sorting household waste, which is included in the organic category, can be processed into compost. Non-organic waste can be handed over to the waste bank to be recycled and made into economically valued materials.

The waste bank coordinates waste management activities in its environment. People who have collected inorganic waste in their homes bring their inorganic waste to the waste bank to save. Inorganic waste management at the waste bank includes weighing, recording, and recording on the customer's waste passbook and the bank book as a guide for waste bank management. The garbage from customers collected in the waste bank is sold to garbage collectors to be used as money. The money will be returned to the customer when the savings are withdrawn following the recorded waste savings. Inorganic waste saved in a waste bank will be sorted and sold according to its type. The waste that can be sold is the waste the recycling industry needs, such as various types of paper, plastic, metal, and glass. Garbage that cannot be recycled by industry can be processed into handicrafts from waste, such as various forms of bags, flowers, or other crafts. The size of the waste bank organization depends on the work area and the number of customers. The organizational structure has at least a director, teller, and seller (garbage seller). Other structures that can be added are waste sorting and packing officers. The process of sorting waste does not require a machine; it manually separates waste according to its type and then sells it. The life of the waste bank is unlimited as long as the community continues to generate waste. The waste bank will only operate if customers save money in the waste bank.

A waste bank is a form of waste management business that can provide economic and non-economic benefits in terms of a cleaner and healthier environment for the community [8]. The unclean living environment within the community has become a social issue in Yogyakarta, both conceptually and practically. The literature review states that the high interest in social entrepreneurship and innovation in recent years is not followed by research examining social innovation. In Indonesia, there needs to be more research on social innovation and entrepreneurship, especially waste bank social entrepreneurship [9]. This research aims to explore the description of entrepreneurship in developing waste banks in Ngalang village, Gunungkidul Regency.

Indicates a high level of public awareness exists regarding household waste management, suggesting that society is cognizant of the need to establish foundational principles for the adoption of sustainable waste management practices and technology [10]. The understanding arises from knowledge and conscience to make pro-environmental behavior even though it is not easy to implement. Therefore, it is necessary to encourage the community to create community empowerment to build independence in human resource development. Public engagement (community, government, and private sector) will be essential in creating effective and collaborative environmental management [11]. The first step in establishing autonomy is gaining economic independence. The first step in building autonomy is establishing financial freedom and controlling the environment; one of the ways is through a waste bank. In practice, this waste bank is more acceptable in the village or rural areas than in the middle class or housing areas. Community empowerment through waste banks is included in informal entrepreneurship, which is carried out based on needs. The rubbish is sold to rubbish traders, and the rubbish bank gets the money from the sale, which is then deposited into people's savings according to the purchase price of the rubbish [12].

The success and operational sustainability of waste banks are affected by many factors, including endorsement from municipal authorities, non-profit entities, corporations, and additional interested parties [13]. The sustainability of waste bank activities as a business activity needs to consider its administrators' ability to manage and develop waste banks so that they become one of the regional economic bodies [14]. Therefore, observing its administrators' entrepreneurial readiness in managing waste banks is crucial.

The ability and willingness of a person to participate in entrepreneurial activity is known as entrepreneurial readiness. Numerous aspects, including as resources, entrepreneurial skills, motivation, and opportunity detection, all have an impact on it [15]. According to Schillo *et al.* [16], entrepreneurial readiness refers to one's ability and willingness to run business activities with the ability to build a social network, have the skills to create the product, perceive failure, and recognize opportunities in their environment. The definition of entrepreneurial readiness is one's level of preparedness or readiness to pursue their own business. Combining psychological, social, and educational elements, entrepreneurial readiness refers to a person's

capacity and inclination to take on entrepreneurial endeavours. It can be defined as an individual's level of preparation or preparedness to pursue a business venture [17]. Entrepreneurial readiness benefits from having high levels of entrepreneurial self-efficacy (ESE) [18]. Based on the description above, entrepreneurship readiness is individuals' ability and willingness to create new businesses with their creative potential in exploring business opportunities around them.

Entrepreneurial readiness, according to Schillo *et al.* [16], consists of four components: i) individuals' skills, which is an individual's belief in the skills they have to effectively organize and carry out the actions required to produce products; ii) fear of failure, it is the fear perceived by individuals over the failure that will be encountered in the process of creating and carrying out a business; iii) Social capital is a social resource that is viewed as an investment to obtain new resources such as relationships, business collaboration, and information; and iv) perceived opportunity is an individual's ability to identify business opportunities around them. Entrepreneurial readiness is essential for someone who starts their business so that they can sustain and develop it. Individuals can interpret emerging business opportunities and solve them to materialize them in business products.

Poor readiness will make entrepreneurs hesitant to create business plans, hesitate when they have to make crucial decisions, and be less productive because they need to be more observant in seeing the opportunities around them [19]. There is a fear that business people are at risk of their business investment, so there is no innovation effort in their business production; eventually, they will lose in business competition [20]. It differs from someone with high entrepreneurial readiness, characterized by the ability to process ideas to create something new and valuable by mobilizing their energy, thoughts, and materials so the business can develop [21], [22]. Someone who has high entrepreneurial readiness has a mindset in creating a business. Based on the explanation above, it is deduced that entrepreneurial readiness is crucial for the waste bank administrators in Ngalang Village to immediately run and maintain a business, create new product innovations, and develop and deal with the dynamics in the entrepreneurial world. Therefore, it is necessary to know the description of the entrepreneurial readiness of the waste bank community in Ngalang Village, Gunungkidul Regency, so that economic-based community empowerment efforts can be adequately actualized. The research question is "How is the entrepreneurial readiness of the waste bank community in developing a waste-based business in Ngalang Village, Gunungkidul ?".

2. METHOD

Phenomenology studies subjective experience and perspective awareness of a subject from various informants encountered. The research method used in this study is qualitative research and uses a phenomenological approach. The objective of the qualitative method is to interpret and study the phenomenon of entrepreneurial readiness in the waste bank administrators by examining the information that informants have given to researchers. The phenomenological approach in this study is to collect data from respondents through interviews, analyze the message based on the informants' experiences, and present data. Then, the data were processed and interpreted to obtain universally explained results [23].

2.1. Research respondent

This study's respondents were six administrators and the waste bank community members in Ngalang Village, Gedangsari, Gunungkidul. Respondents were selected using a purposive sampling technique with the characteristics of the respondents: administrators and members of the Ngalang Village waste bank, do not have a permanent job, have an active status, and have been involved for at least one year. The respondent identity of the waste bank administrator and member can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Respondents' identity of the waste bank administrator and member

Informant	1	2	3	4	5
Name (Initial)	Mrs. P	Mrs. N	Mrs. Y and Mrs. S	Mrs. A	Mr. W (Advisor)
Neighborhood	RT 01	RT 02	RT 03	RT 04	RT 01
Age (Years)	37	39	35 and 38	40	62
Level of education	Elementary school	Junior high school	Junior high school	Junior high school	Elementary school

2.2. Data collection method

This research implements a semi-structured interview as the data collection method, consisting of the interview guide the researchers have arranged. The interview guide is prepared based on entrepreneurial readiness, Schillo *et al.* [16] theory. The aspects include: i) individual skills, ii) fear of failure, iii) social capital, and iv)

perceived opportunity. Before starting the interview, the researcher also built a rapport with the respondent. Passive respondent observation is also carried out while conducting interviews to support the interview method.

2.3. Research trustworthiness

The researchers apply the strategy of member checking to the respondent as the finding's accuracy of the transcribed aspects. This checking also serves to maintain high standards of credibility. Subsequently, to increase the research credibility, researchers used prolonged engagement by spending sufficient time to understand the waste bank administrators' entrepreneurial readiness while increasing the credibility of the data that had been collected. The last stage of data collection is to conduct discussions with other researchers (peer debriefing) to improve research accuracy.

2.4. Data analysis

The data analysis employed in this research is content analysis. The content analysis technique is a technique that emphasizes images, themes, words, symbols, and meanings that are generated after interview results. Steps in conducting analysis based on theory by Creswell [23], which states that the research uses a phenomenological approach that processes data using content analysis techniques, including:

- a. Describing the informant's experience related to the studied phenomenon.
- b. Making a list of essential questions (guide) according to the phenomenon and about how the informant experienced the phenomenon based on the results of the interview.
- c. Highlighting meaning units, groups of important statements, and making the information wider.
- d. Describing what and how research informants experience the phenomena.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of interviews with six respondents show that the entrepreneurial readiness of the waste bank community is divided into nine aspects. They are individual skills, fear of failure, social capital, perceived opportunity, physical, mental, and spiritual preparation, personality development preparation, business activity preparation, and product marketing capability preparation. The results will be explained based on the following aspects.

3.1. Individual skills

A different Indonesian study discovered a favourable relationship between entrepreneurial preparedness and entrepreneurial self-efficacy (ESE) [24]. Personal competency is defined as the ability that individuals have to operationalize in concrete situations a set of knowledge, attitudes, and skills to be successful [25], [26]. A person with skills in a particular area has analytical and creative abilities, more than just basic knowledge of performance conditions. Individuals demonstrate special competence when they successfully operationalize their expertise in certain situations. The following is an excerpt from the interview:

"...previously, they taught us to make flowers out of plastic, we can make plastic flowers, but we have never made them again, now..." (Informant 1, RT 01)

"...in our waste bank activities, we make rice husk fertilizer and do gardening. We work together with people in RT 4 for gardening; I suppose we don't have particular skills because we only work on collecting waste and making husk fertilizer, and the gardening is done together..." (Informant 2, RT 02)

"...there used to be a training for handicrafts out of plastic cup waste, but that was a long time ago, I think around 2019, if I'm not mistaken, we can make tissue boxes and some crafty items some sort, But we never made it again, now, so I forgot how to do it again..." (Informant 3, RT 03)

"...at the beginning of founding the waste bank, we were taught to make organic fertilizer from vegetable waste, fruit peels, banana watermelons. Then we were also taught how to run the waste bank..." (Informant 4, RT 04)

"...plastics waste were sorted, it can be turned into accessories craft items..." (Informant 5, Advisor, RT 01)

"...it takes painstaking to choose and sort waste so that it can be more valuable..." (Informant 5, Advisor, RT 01)

Entrepreneurial skills are understood as the knowledge, attitudes, and skills that enable someone to be successful in developing original and valuable projects, products, or services based on the needs of a company target, population, and, as a result, the fulfillment of functional, social, or emotional objectives [27]. Entrepreneurial skills are a motivating factor for businesses to maintain their product quality. The excellent image they get from customers and the income rate will increase if qualified business put in all their skills and knowledge that can trigger the development of entrepreneurial skills. It makes good habits and makes businesses sensitive to changes in the business environment, both internal and external environment [28].

3.2. Fear of failure

Fear of failure is the fear that individuals feel about a loss they will experience when creating or founding and doing business [16]. The research show that a number of factors, such as perceived entrepreneurial self-confidence, perceived ease of establishing a firm, societal norms, education, funding availability, and perceived government policy, all have an impact on entrepreneurial fear of failure [29]. The following is an excerpt from the interview.

"...that is the challenge because, in RT 01, there are many elderly folks, so collecting their trash is hard, especially when Coronavirus struck; it didn't work for two years. I think we should not stop gathering around to collect the waste..." (Informant 1, RT 01)

"...there's no such thing because waste bank activities are based on individual awareness. We also sell to collectors individually. For making husk fertilizer, we only did it when we do regular social gatherings..." (Informant 2, RT 02)

"...in RT 03, the waste bank has stopped for two years, during the pandemic, because the government forbids people to gather around, so we stopped for two years and only recently started again..." "I guess the problem is, sometimes there's no waste to collect, not every month we have incoming waste, additionally, for these gathering activities, sometimes we postpone because sometimes they collide with other important scheduled events, such as a cultural festival event, and this month there are national independence week events, Ms..." (Informant 3, RT 03)

"...in the past couple of years, during the pandemic, the waste bank did not stop at all, we just couldn't gather around to deposit the waste, so the activity was changed to depositing money for savings so that the activities don't stop..." (Informant 4, RT 04)

"...we don't dare enough to try this on a large scale; we do it little by little; the most important is that we got something to work on..." (Informant 5, Advisor, RT 01)

The interview results imply that the respondents have risk calculations that they will face when carrying out business activities such as managing a waste bank. It raises the ability to anticipate the possibilities resulting in the activity's failure. Fear of failure can make it difficult for entrepreneurs to pursue their business pursuits, but it can also motivate them [30]. Other research explains that negative emotional states can give entrepreneurs a negative view of an opportunity [20]. Demonstrate the influence of a variety of factors on entrepreneurial fear of failure, including perceived ease of starting a business, societal norms, education, funding availability, and government policies [29]. Research indicates that educational initiatives have a noteworthy and favourable impact on the entrepreneurial mentality and competencies, including financial literacy, creativity, and planning [31].

3.3. Social capital

The concept of social capital is broad and encompasses assets, connections, and profits. Interactions and behaviours within an agent-controlled system that adhere to mutually agreed-upon norms, commitments, and guidelines activate it [32]. This aspect reflects the relationship of a group of individuals who create value and facilitate action in a social structure. The following is an excerpt from the interview.

"...so far, we only sold the waste to garbage collectors..." (Informant 1, RT 01)

"... Besides collectors, we also have Wisma Village. This village has activities such as social gatherings, and we also collaborate with KWT (Women Farmers Group); the activities are planting living stalls, living pharmacies, gardening, and doing it together with making husk fertilizer..." (Informant 2, RT 02)

"...as far as I know, there have been no activities together with other communities, and we only do activities with members and administrators of RT 03; we still do the same for the collectors to sell the collected waste..." (Informant 3, RT 03)

"...to sell it, we only go to waste collectors..." (Informant 4, RT 04)

"...this activity was originally only for socializing and gathering amongst residents; the point is to help each other, and this activity is beneficial..." (Informant 5, Advisor, RT 01)

The interview results indicate that the respondents have several relationships in waste bank activities. Good social capital will make it easier for people to participate in collective action as a form of caring for each other [33]. Social networks shape people's actions and influence community resilience [33]. People can share opportunities, resources, and knowledge with one another through social networks. They may also have an impact on decisions and behaviour within the network. A study on self-disclosure decisions on social networks found that the two choice stages of creating a post and providing information need distinct cognitive and affective processes [34]. They facilitate the sharing of opportunities, resources, and information between people and groups. Studies on social network self-disclosure decisions, social network disaster management, and trust-consensus multiplex networks in group decision-making have illustrated how social networks impact behaviour and decisions inside the network [35]. One of the most important entrepreneurial abilities for professional success is networking, along with cooperation. In the framework of the present globalisation and digital transformation phenomena, a study sought to characterise and systematise these abilities, resulting in the identification of a tripartite entrepreneurial skills model that incorporates networking and teamwork [36]. Subsequent research demonstrated that students who participated in the Student Entrepreneurial Attachment Project (SEAP), which provided them with a real-world business experience, acquired entrepreneurial networking skills related to collaboration and communication [37]. Entrepreneurial engineers that possess networking, teamwork, opportunity recognition, innovation, risk management, and discipline-specific talents will be the future's most successful people [38]. Additionally, a research highlights the significance of networking and teamwork in opportunity discovery and exploitation, emphasising the role of human interactions skills (HIS) in the success of the entrepreneurial process [39]. Among the entrepreneurial skills necessary to be successful professionally, teamwork and networking also stand out [40]. Social capital is the collective term for the networks, resources, and connections that people and organisations can use to accomplish their objectives. When it comes to entrepreneurial abilities, social capital can assist people in creating a solid professional network, spotting fresh prospects, and fostering relationships based on mutual respect and cooperation [41].

3.4. Perceived opportunity

Many elements, including as consumer demands, technology developments, market trends, perceived pressure, perceived rationalisation, and perceived competency, might affect perceived opportunity [42]. This aspect reflects individuals who can see business opportunities and interpret them so they can be applied to business products. The following is an excerpt from the interview.

"...we think that rather than waste, it's better to collect it and make the village cleaner, even though the money is not much, but we are more concerned about how to make this garbage not wasted and pollute the village..." (Informant 1, RT 01)

"...we set up a waste bank to keep the environment clean. We save money from the waste bank results, and then we can use the savings to buy fertilizer for gardening and living stalls. From the results of making husk fertilizer, live stalls, and live pharmacies, we sell the output; from there, we can add shared savings for the residents of RT 2..." (Informant 2, RT 02)

"...in the beginning, we saw that women in RT 01 were arranging a waste bank, so we, the ladies of RT 03, are also interested in doing it. So, we will also establish a waste bank for RT 03., besides we can make the environment clean, we also earn money for saving..." ...because the waste bank activity is just collecting and sorting garbage and saving the money, no other activities I suppose..." (Informant 3, RT 03)

"...at first, instead of us, the garbage was picked up by people outside the area; I was not too fond of it. I mean, instead of being used by other people, someone else will get the benefit, you know, we should manage it, and we can also get the profits..." (Informant 4, RT 04)

"...currently the activities are more about utilizing used goods/waste into money..." (Informant 5, Advisor, RT 01)

The interview results indicate that the respondents can take advantage of opportunities from the garbage in their environment. Respondents can see that the previously considered worthless waste can also have economic value if treated properly. Ways to handle and process waste to produce revenue [43]. Individuals who have a perception of opportunity can develop an interest in running a business. In addition to increasing economic gains from managing inorganic waste [44], treating organic waste can also yield financial gains [45]. Identifying entrepreneurial opportunities is the main thing in the initial steps of individuals who will become entrepreneurs, as a process of understanding and assessing the market correctly and as a human resource process to learn about business, hone the ability to innovate, and build personality [46]. Perceived opportunity for entrepreneurship is positively and significantly related to entrepreneurial activity [47]. The greater the business opportunities perceived by the management and members of the waste bank, the greater their entrepreneurial activities will be. Perceived opportunity also mediates in linking perceived ability with entrepreneurial intention. In the process of starting a business, perceived opportunity is important [48]. The business opportunities that a person perceives can encourage the emergence of entrepreneurial intentions, and these entrepreneurial intentions make a person more ready to become an entrepreneur or start a business. Entrepreneurial readiness can also be seen through the elements mentioned by Pardiman and Khoirul [49], which include individual physical, mental, and spiritual preparation, personality preparation, preparation of personality development, preparation of business activities, and preparation of product marketing capabilities.

3.5. Individual physical, mental, and spiritual preparation

Physical, mental, and spiritual preparation is essential in preparing for entrepreneurship. If an individual's physical, mental, and spiritual aspects are at a good stage of readiness, they will be in harmony to increase their entrepreneurial readiness [49]. The following is an excerpt from the interview.

"...the young women who are active in collecting and helping weigh, they are more enthusiastic and enjoy the activity, the young women are diligent in collecting the waste..." (Informant 1, RT 01)

"We collect the waste on our own, individually, and sell it to the collectors individually, but we make husk fertilizer together. Later, the younger women will focus on husk fertilizer. Gardening is for us who are already old because gardening is not too heavy. We have good times when we gather around because we can share activities; when we get together, we will discuss waste bank activities with others..." (Informant 2, RT 02)

"...for the residents in RT 03, we are actively participating in the waste bank, collecting garbage too. Whenever there's waste incoming, we do all the sorting, and some help to weigh the waste; there is also someone who helps write in the book..." (Informant 3, RT 03)

"...if it is me, I'm ready to run this waste bank, we just do it first, don't over think or afraid what others might say..." (Informant 4, RT 04)

"...in the waste bank, we just go with the flow; women here have positive activities to help each other with a social gathering and at the same time utilize the waste to be sold..." (Informant 5, Advisor, RT 01)

Studies have indicated a connection between a number of well-being factors, such as depression, life satisfaction, positive and negative affect, and conscientiousness, openness, agreeableness, and neuroticism, and personality qualities like these [50]. A person's ability to feel well and perform well, feel happy and content, realise their potential, have some control over their lives, have a purpose in life, and have healthy connections are all considered aspects of well-being [51]. Well-being is an individual's state described as a feeling of happiness, satisfaction, physical and mental health, and a good quality of life. Apart from that, entrepreneurs run their businesses based on spiritual beliefs in their mission and goals, such as intelligent spiritual beliefs, affirmation of spiritual beliefs, and turning beliefs into action [52]. Spiritual beliefs accumulated through learning and experience accentuate trust in business relationships [52]. Physical, mental and spiritual preparation factors are related to the description of the entrepreneurial readiness of the Ngalang Village community in developing community empowerment through waste banks.

3.6. Personality preparation

Personality is one of the determinants of success in running a business. This personality is related to the success of the business he runs. That a person's personality can have a substantial impact on their subjective well-being, which is a measure of their overall happiness and life satisfaction [50]. Entrepreneurs with certain personality traits, such as extraversion or conscientiousness, may be more likely to engage in successful entrepreneurial activities. The research results indicate that personality is associated with financial well-being, which can be relevant to entrepreneurial success [53]. The following is an excerpt from the interview.

"...me and the women in this KWT really like this activity; we feel enthusiastic..." (Informant 1, RT 01)

"...we as administrators already said to the residents to separate the waste based on its types so that the sales process to collectors will get more results..." (Informant 2, RT 02)

"...people here in RT 03 because seeing the waste bank in RT 01 is interesting and the environment is clean too, so we are interested in forming a waste bank in RT 03. The women concurrently agreed to the plan, so we all jumped in..." (Informant 3, RT 03)

"Several households are participating in the waste bank, and only 10 out of 32 households are participating. It is voluntary, there is no coercion, and many don't participate because they are not detailed in collecting their waste. Moreover, some residents who are a bit rich are reluctant..." (Informant 4, RT 04)

"...I am sure that this waste bank activity will develop and become one of the contributors to residents' income..." (Informant 5, Advisor, RT 01)

Personality can accurately predict entrepreneurial behavior. The five personality dimensions are conscientiousness, introversion/extraversion, openness to experience, agreeableness, and neuroticism. These dimensions are considered the most comprehensive and widely accepted framework for understanding personality [54]. The interview results show that the subject has a strong personality, such as confidence, optimism, enthusiasm, passion, voluntary behavior, involvement, and mutual help, which can help him/her be better prepared to become a waste bank entrepreneur.

3.7. Preparation of skills development

Entrepreneurship is a skill that is indirectly formed without experience and development so that entrepreneurial readiness can be formed [49]. Developing skills is an entrepreneur's effort in managing their business or ventures because the skills will make the business run, grow, and succeed. It takes a certain set of abilities to build entrepreneurship, including perseverance, communication, and opportunity finding [55]. It is hoped that entrepreneurs will first prepare their entrepreneurial skills. The following is an excerpt from the interview.

"...at first, we got it from UAD students through the Community Service Program. They taught how to manage this waste bank, and they were also taught how to make flowers out of plastic; actually, we need to be taught so that the waste is not only sold to collectors but can be processed into other goods because so far I'm the one made the waste for livestock food..." (Informant 1, RT 01)

"...we want a training held to develop this waste bank, at the beginning of establishing the waste bank, we had training but only once. The training is making charcoal from wood, but it's elliptical. For now, if there is another training, we want to follow it..." (Informant 2, RT 02)

"...in the early days of this waste bank, there was training on handicrafts from plastic waste, and they also taught us to make tissue boxes. For now, we need more training, such as training on making fertilizer or training on utilizing waste into goods that are ready to use and also ready to be traded..." (Informant 3, RT 03)

"...we hope that there is a training like making crafts, something like that, things are made from garbage, or we can make wicker from bamboo because there are a lot of bamboo plants around here..." (Informant 4, RT 04)

"...I hope that someone trains the residents here, there used to be a resident who gave training here, but he passed away, so they stopped training activities..." (Informant 5, Advisor, RT 01)

The interview results indicate that the respondents intend to follow the training to develop the waste bank business. Skills development is an important thing that is necessary for entrepreneurship and has become a challenge for the younger generation along with technological developments [56]. Entrepreneurial skills can improve entrepreneurial abilities by encouraging someone to dare to take risks, identify practical business methods, and be prepared to take advantage of all existing opportunities. The research results provide evidence that entrepreneurial skills are essential for success in starting and running a business [57]. Development of entrepreneurial skills to increase entrepreneurial intentions through entrepreneurship education [58]. Entrepreneurial skills consist of personal skills and business skills. Personal skills and business skills need to be developed by entrepreneurs to create and manage innovative businesses. Critical thinking, inventiveness, and adaptability are examples of non-cognitive personal characteristics that are crucial for an entrepreneurial attitude and orientation [59].

3.8. Business activities preparation

Business activities are an essential part of entrepreneurship. Business activities can also be referred to as ventures, which carry out activities sustainably, consistently, and continuously to achieve goals and earn a profit [60]. A business activity that is directed, mature, and sensitive to the scope of the market is an essential component of entrepreneurship readiness [49]. The following is an excerpt from the interview.

"...so every Selapanan we collect the waste here, the collected garbage has been separated and sorted when it is collected here, but if before Selapanan, they want to store it here, they may. The garbage collectors come and weigh them individually, so it's not all put together but per household. So the waste amount will be different and go into the savings book..." (Informant 1, RT 01)

"...we have now developed a waste bank, sometimes we make husk fertilizer, this fertilizer is for sale, now it has been sold quite a lot, and we are also developing live pharmacies and live stalls. Currently, we have ten types of live pharmacies, 15 types of live stalls plants..." (Informant 2, RT 02)

"...every second week of the month, we gather at Mrs. Beti's house for garbage collection; from that house, the waste has been sorted first, so when we are at Mrs. Beti's house, we just sell it to garbage collectors, and record how much the income is in the waste bank book..." (Informant 3, RT 03)

"...the activity here is held every 10th of the month, and the activity is collecting waste and regular community gatherings. Then, if I have collected a lot of garbage, I will sort it out, then it will be sold to collectors, the money will be put into a savings book, we also use the collected money for savings and loans for members..." (Informant 4, RT 04)

"...eventually we also need directions on how to sell products made from recycled waste because we are still new to selling such goods..." (Informant 5, Advisor, RT 01)

The interview results imply that the respondents or members of the waste bank in Ngalang Village have similarities in setting up their businesses. Still, each has its way of operating. Referring to Hisrich *et al.* [61], several elements become the principal capital for individuals to set up for the course of business: perseverance, creativity, enthusiasm, and not giving up easily. A business plan will provide convenience in making plans and formulating the requirements to carry out business strategies and achieve business goals. A comprehensive corporate plan emphasises the need of adapting to modern business practices in many ways, such as the implementation of an AI-integrated mobile application. This can increase the company's audience reach and enhance client comfort and accessibility [62].

3.9. Preparation of product marketing capabilities

The ability to market products is essential because, with a marketing strategy, a business can achieve its goals or objectives. The ability to produce and sell competitive commodities in external markets is a prerequisite for increasing the competitiveness of governments and regions [63]. Entrepreneurs can market their products favorably so the business can progress and develop to the next level [49]. The following is an excerpt from the interview.

"...we only market and sell the waste to garbage collectors..." (Informant 1, RT 01)

"...as I told you before, we have started selling husk fertilizer, but if the customer wants to buy it, they contact me directly and go to my house; because the fertilizer is stored in my house, we want the husk fertilizer to be sold in the market or a shop..." (Informant 2, RT 02)

"...the garbage is sold to collectors who usually come..." (Informant 3, RT 03)

"...for the sales, we only go to garbage collectors..." (Informant 4, RT 04)

"...we also want to learn how to sell online, we can buy everything online, it is practical now..." (Informant 5, Advisor, RT 01)

"...later if there is a place to accommodate the sorted waste, the selling price will be higher to the collectors, it is necessary to be patient in sorting the waste..." (Informant 5, Advisor, RT 01)

The interview results imply that the respondents can market the waste bank activities outcome that has been carried out. Waste bank activities include saving waste that has been sorted according to the type of waste. In marketing, companies create value for customers and build strong customer relationships to capture value from customers in return [64]. Marketing is the process of planning and executing the conception, pricing, promotion, and distribution of goods and services to facilitate exchanges that satisfy individuals and companies that cannot serve the organizational objectives [65]. In other studies, understanding the market, employing relevant marketing strategies, and focusing on customer satisfaction are important for shaping consumer behavior and improving financial performance [66].

4. CONCLUSION

Entrepreneurial readiness in the waste bank community in Ngalang Village, Gedangsari Subdistrict, Gunungkidul Regency, is described as the individual belief that the skill they have can produce business products, the emerging ability to anticipate failure in waste bank activity, having several relations to cooperate in marketing the collected waste and taking advantage of opportunities from waste that is considered worthless in the environment so that it can be processed to have a higher selling value. The physical, mental, and spiritual abilities of businesses are an essential foundation in the attempts to prepare themselves to respond to the risks that may arise in running a waste bank business. Various personality dynamics are found in individuals who run waste banks, the wishes to develop skills and knowledge, different business preparations yet still have their characteristics in each waste bank group, and limitations in product marketing.

Efforts to sort, process, and utilize plastic waste into goods of economic value have not been maximized because there needs to be trained personnel in the waste bank, so they are still unable to optimize the existing waste processing. Waste bank administrators must improve their abilities to increase waste's value into more valuable goods. Training is needed to enhance the sustainability of the waste bank, such as waste management training, waste weighing and recording training, bookkeeping training, or waste bank passbook management. In addition, the ability to build communication, socialization, management, and development planning is necessary to make waste bank members ready to make waste bank activities into social entrepreneurship activities in the context of empowering the Ngalang Village community. The government has a supervisory role in the waste bank. In several places, the government provided assistance in the form of waste sorting equipment for customers and waste bank operational equipment such as savings books.

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